

sodium and potassium do not interfere in these titrations. But the green colour of nickel sulphate interferes with the indicator colour change of naphthol blue black while such difficulty does not appear with the colour changes of amaranth and brilliant ponceau 5R. Similarly the pink colour of cobalt chloride interferes with the indicator colour changes of amaranth and brilliant ponceau 5R while it does not interfere in the case of naphthol blue black. Copper(II), arsenic(III), mercury(II), cysteine, thiourea, thioglycolic acid, sulphide, sulphite, thiosulphate interfere at all concentrations.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (K. R. R.) wishes to express his deep sense of gratitude to the authorities of the Andhra University for the award of University Research Fellowship.

References

1. A. BERKA, J. VULTERIN and J. ZYKA, "Newyer Redox Titrants", Pergamon Press, 1965, p. 162.
- 1a. *Ibid.*, p. 56.
2. A. J. LORENZ, R. W. RENOLDS and S. J. W. STEVANS, Symposium on Vitamins, 92 meeting of Amer. Chem. Soc., Pittsburg Pa., 1936.
3. BALLENTINE, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Edn.*, 1941, 13, 89.
4. L. SZEKERES, E. SUGAR and E. POP, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1951, 121, 17.
5. J. CIHALIK, Doctoral thesis, University of Chem. Technology, Prague, 1957.
6. G. GOPALA RAO and V. NARAYANA RAO, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1955, 147, 338.
7. L. ERDEY and E. BODOR, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1952, 24, 418. cf. *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1952/53, 137, 293.
- 7a. L. ERDEY and L. KAPLAR, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1958, 162, 180.
8. G. S. DESHMUKH and M. G. BAPAT, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1955, 145, 254.
9. B. SINGH, G. P. KASHYAP and S. S. SAHOTA, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1958, 162, 357.
10. E. SCHULEK, J. KOVAES and R. ROZSA, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1951, 121, 17.
11. I. M. KOLTHOFF, et. al. Volumetric Analysis, III. Interscience publisher, Inc., New York, 1957, pp. 222, 231.

Identification of Sugars and Organic Acids in Bananas

D. L. PATIL and N. G. MAGAR

Department of Biochemistry, Institute of Science,
Bombay 400 032

Manuscript received 12 September 1975; revised 21 December 1975; accepted 19 March 1976

THE most conspicuous change in ripening of bananas is the conversion of starch to sugars and changes in flavour. Wali and Hassan¹ reported the presence of glucose, fructose and sucrose in bananas. Lulla and Johar² detected sugars in south Indian bananas. Wyman and Palmer³ identified and malic, citric and oxalic acids

in ripe Gros Michel banana. The present study reports the identification of sugars and organic acids by chromatography in bananas viz. Basrai, Harichal, Lalkel (variety of *Musa cavendishii*), Rajeli, Safed velchi (variety of *Musa paradisiaca*) cultivated around the coast of Bombay, Maharashtra State. The purpose of the present communication is to report the various sugars and organic acids detected on paper chromatogram in the indigenous varieties of ripen bananas.

Experimental

Sugars: 20 g. of banana pulp were homogenised with 70% alcohol for the extraction of sugars. The alcoholic slurry was strained through a cheese cloth and centrifuged. The clear extracts were made alcohol free on a water bath and made upto a known volume. The presence of sugars in banana pulp extract solvent-5 *n*-butanol-acetic acid-water (4 : 1 : 5) was used as developer and aniline hydrogen phthalate⁶ as spraying reagent and location of the various sugar spots was identified.

Organic acids: 50 g. of banana pulp were extracted in cold with two volumes of 70% alcohol. The supernatants were concentrated and made upto a known volume. The extracts were directly passed through an anion exchange column of Dowex-1 (200-400 mesh) in the formate form to absorb all the organic acids. The organic acids were fractionally displaced from the column with 4 *N* formic acid. The elutes containing organic acids were freed of formic acid by evaporating to dryness under reduced pressure at 40°. The dried sample was redissolved in 0.8 ml of 5 *N* sulphuric acid and slurried with one gram of silica gel. This slurry was then transferred to a silica gel column and the acids were separated and identified as outlined by Marvel and Rands⁷.

Results and Discussion

It was observed that paper chromatographic separation of sugars in bananas showed the presence of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose. Maki et. al⁸ reported the presence of glucose, fructose and sucrose in ripe Taiwan bananas. Poland et al⁹ identified glucose, fructose, sucrose as the major sugars in banana pulp. Lulla and Johar² analysed the sugars in different species of bananas. The present findings are in accordance with those reported by Lulla and Johar and confirmed. It was also found that among organic acids, citric and malic acids were detected in all varieties of bananas studied in the present investigation. Palmer and Wyman³ reported the presence of citric, malic and oxalic acids in high concentration. Edward Ross et al¹⁰ identified small quantities of phosphoric acid in addition to citric and malic acid in chinese banana. Lulla and Johar¹¹ determined organic acids and reported that citric and malic acids were present. In the present findings malic acid was found to be predominant among the samples studied.

Acknowledgements

Thanks are due to University Grants Commission for the award of financial assistance to one of us (DLP)

for this research. Thanks are also due to Mr. Prabhakar H. Raut for supplying bananas.

References

1. Y. A. WALI and Y. M. HASSAN., *Proc. Amer. Soc. Hort. Sci.*, 1965, **87**, 264.
2. B. S. LULLA and D.S. JOHAR., *Current Sci.*, 1955, **24**, 92.
3. H. WYMAN and J. K. PALMER., *Plant Physiology*, 1964, **39**, 630.
4. S.M. PATRIDGE., *Biochem. J.*, 1948, **42**, 238.
5. K. H. SLOTTA and J. PRIMOSIGH. *Nature*, 1951, **168**, 696.
6. S. M. PARTRIDGE, *Nature*, 1943, **164**, 443.
7. C. S. MARVEL and R. D. RANDS, (Jr.) *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 2642.
8. M. MAKI and Y. SATO., *Kaseigaku-Zasshi*, 1959, **20**, 406.
9. G. L. POLAND, H. W. VON LOESECKE, M. W. BRENNER., J. T. MANION and P. L. HARRIS, *Food Res.*, 1937, **2**, 403.
10. EDWARD ROSS and C. L. MILLER., *Food Sci.*, 1963, **28**, 193.
11. B. S. LULLA and D.S. JOHAR, *Current Sci.*, 1954, **23**, 362.

Reaction of Benzyne with Carboxylic Acids

R. S. PAL*, R. P. SHARMA and M. M. BOKADIA

School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University,
Ujjain (M. P.)

Manuscript received 29 July 1975 ; accepted 18 February 1976

GENERAL survey of literature reveals that little work has been done on the reactions of benzyne with carboxylic acids¹⁻⁸. We, therefore, studied the reactions of benzyne with chlorobenzoic acids,

When anthranilic acid was used as substrate, the primary amino group is preferentially phenylated to that of -COOH group, hence accounting for our obtaining N-phenylanthranilic acid. However, increase in reaction time at elevated temperatures afforded N, N-diphenyl phenyl anthranilate, i. e., -NH₂ and -COOH groups were fully phenylated. But in any case it was not possible to isolate N, N-diphenylanthranilic acid, N-phenyl-phenylanthranilate or phenylanthranilate.

Our careful and repeated experiment with salicylic acid yielded only phenyl salicylate and formation of *o*-phenoxybenzoic acid or *o*-phenoxy phenylbenzoate was not observed at all.

The yields are reported only of benzoates or maximum phenylated final products.

The results are summarised in the following table :

Acknowledgements

We are indebted to CSIR, New Delhi for a junior research fellowship to one of us (RSP).

References

1. M. STILES, R. G. MILLER and U. BURCKHARDT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 1792.
2. R. HOWE, *J. Chem. Soc.(C)*, 1966, 478.
3. S. F. SYKE, A. R. MARSHALL and J. P. WATSON, *Tetrahedron*, 1966, **22**, 2515.
4. E. MCNELIS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 3188.

Sl. No.	Substrate	Product†	m.p. (°C)*	Yield (%) Procedure	
				(a)	(b)
1.	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid	Phenyl- <i>o</i> -chlorobenzoate	36-37	22	34
2.	<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid	Phenyl- <i>m</i> -chlorobenzoate	52-53	22	33
3.	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid	Phenyl- <i>p</i> -chlorobenzoate	100	27	44
4.	Phenoxyacetic acid	Phenyl-phenoxy acetate	54-56	24	32
5.	Salicylic acid	Phenyl salicylate	41-43	28	47
6.	Anthranilic acid	N,N-Diphenyl-phenyl-anthranilate	83-84	9	-

* All the m.p.'s are uncorrected.

† Characterisation of products was done by m.p., m.m.p., Co-TLC and ir spectra comparison with that of authentic sample.

phenoxyacetic acid etc. The reactions were carried out in dry THF and procedures⁹ (a) and (b) were followed for the generation of benzyne. When benzene was used as reaction medium in place of THF biphenyl was obtained besides corresponding benzoate. However, when procedure¹⁰ (b) was followed acridone was inevitable product irrespective of the solvent used.

* Present address : Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology. Kanpur-208016.

5. P. SARTORI and M. WEIDENBRUCH, *Angew. Chem.*, 1965, **77**, 1076 ; *Angew.Chem. Internat. Ed.* 1965, **4**, 1072.
6. H. E. SIMMONS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 691.
7. G. KOBRICH, *Chem. Ber.*, 1963, **96**, 2544.
8. R. W. HOFFMANN, "Dehydrobenzene and Cycloalkynes", Academic Press, New York, 1966.
9. M. STILES and R. G. MILLER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1960, **82**, 3802.
10. L. FRIEDMAN and F. M. LOGULLO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 1549.